

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Legume Inclusion in Potato Cropping Systems Improves Soil Fertility and Reduces Agrochemical Dependency

One of the main agricultural challenges in potato cultivation within the Lusitanian pedoclimatic region is the need for high rates of external fertilizer to achieve adequate yields. However, these inputs cause soil and water pollution and reduce soil biodiversity.

To address this, one potential agronomic practice is the inclusion of a leguminous crop in the rotation. Therefore, a field experiment was conducted replacing wheat with pea in the rotation, changing the conventional rotation cycle from potato-wheat-potato to potato-pea-potato.

The results obtained were highly satisfactory. In this sense, the legume effectively fixed nitrogen (N) in the soil, increasing NH_4^+ content by 35% compared to the conventional treatment.

Additionally, there was a greater abundance of genes involved in carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles, along with a 28% rise in NO_3^- content. This nitrogen fixation allowed a 50% reduction in cover fertilizer application in the following potato cycle.

Remarkably, despite the reduced fertilizer input, potato yield in the legume rotation was 21% higher than in the conventional cycle (Figure 1).

These findings show that introducing peas into the rotation significantly enhances soil fertility, reduces fertilizer needs, improves potato yield, and boosts soil biodiversity while mitigating the environmental impacts of synthetic fertilizers.

1. Potato yield under the two tested rotational systems: conventional (potato-wheat-potato) and legume-based (potato-pea-potato).

KEYWORDS

Potato cultivation; crop diversification; legume inclusion; soil fertility; soil biodiversity; fertilizers; agricultural practice; sustainable agriculture.

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